

Xist controls metabolic fitness.

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Xist was originally discovered for its role in dosage compensation in females in the Barr Body. Our group demonstrated that the Xist and a recently defined RNP complex, the Xist RNP, is a central effector of transformation in human cells. We later demonstrated separate roles for Xist in normal gene regulation associated with its dosage compensation function in somatic cells. Here we demonstrate that Xist controls metabolic fitness. Knockout of Xist in human cells resulted in profound metabolic alterations including activation of oxoglutarate dehydrogenase (*OGDH*) and succinate dehydrogenase complex subunit D (*SDHD*), together with silencing of oxoglutarate dehydrogenase-like (*OGDHL*) and 2-oxoglutarate and iron-dependent oxygenase domain containing 3 (*OGFOD3*). Among the most significantly perturbed genes transcriptome-wide in Xist *-/-* cells were the FAD-dependent oxidoreductase domain containing genes *FOXRED1* and *FOXRED2*. Xist deletion resulted in silencing of glutamic-pyruvic transaminase 2 (*GPT2*) with concomitant activation of glutamine-fructose-6-phosphate transaminase 2 (*GFPT2*). Loss of Xist in human stem cells resulted in aberrant activation of *IDH2*. Xist controls metabolic fitness separately from and in concert with its epigenetic functions at the chromatin.

Citations

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